

ELASTICITY SOLUTION OF POLYMERIC PIEZOELECTRIC C-BLOCK COMPOSITE ACTUATOR

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SUMMARY: An elasticity solution is developed to investigate the mechanical behavior of polymeric piezoelectric C-block composite actuators, which were recently proposed to overcome the limitations of conventional bimorph and stack configurations. The stress functions are used to derive the general equations governing the behavior of induced strain actuation under various load conditions. Closed-form expressions are presented for the displacements and stresses. Comparisons of present approach are made with classical elasticity solutions for curved beams and existing approximate solutions for curved actuators for a simplified case. The results from the current solution also provide physical insight into the mechanism of C-block actuators.

KEYWORDS: elasticity solution, c-block, actuator, smart structures, induced strain

INTRODUCTION

Smart materials have received considerable attention in recent years for vibration control, shape control, damage assessment and active noise reduction of engineering structures^[1]. The advantage of incorporating these type of materials into the structure is that the sensing and actuation mechanisms become an internal part of the structure by sensing and actuating strain directly. The application of smart materials is currently being investigated for in rotary- and fixed-wing aircrafts and large flexible space structures. Significant effort has been focused on piezoelectric materials due to their fast response, low power consumption and relative large induced strain for an applied voltage. The limitations of most commonly used flat bimorph configuration include relatively smaller deflections and the low forces. Therefore, a new class of polymeric piezoelectric composite actuators, called C-blocks (Fig.1) because of their curved shape, has been developed to overcome the limitations of conventional bimorph and stack piezoelectric configurations. These actuators have been shown better force and deflection capabilities^[2].

Since the concept of curved actuators is relatively new, very few research efforts have been reported in developing rigorous mathematical models for investigating the mechanical behavior of the C-block actuators. Questions still remain regarding a complete understanding of the physical phenomena involved. The research was initiated by Brei who developed an approximate approach using the curved Bernoulli-Euler beam model which is only valid in pure bending cases^[2,3]. Castigliano's second theorem was employed to derive the end

deflection, the end force and the end moment. Later, Seeley, Chattopadhyay and Brei presented a new hybrid optimization procedure to optimize the design of the C-block actuators by using this approximate curved beam model^[4]. Recently, Chattopadhyay, Mitchell and Gu developed the refined approach based on the first-order shear deformation theory to overcome the limitation of the pure bending assumptions^[5]. The major limitations of the approximate curved beam model are pure bending assumption and the inplane displacement distribution through the thickness, particularly for laminates in which the stiffness properties vary dramatically from layer to layer. Another important limiting factor is that the beam-type constitutive relations eliminate the possibility of rigorous calculation of interlaminar stresses. For actuators, the curved beam solution also does not account for the local effect of the induced strain, which eventually changes the stress and displacement distributions in multi-layered actuators.

Fig.1 Geometry of a piezoelectric C-block actuator

As a remedy to these limitations, the elasticity solution is developed for this class of polymeric piezoelectric C-block composite actuators in this paper. The general behaviors of the C-block actuator are classified, for a convenient solution procedure, as the combination of the actuator with only the induced stain, the actuator with only the end moment and the actuator with only the end force. The governing equations are derived and solution forms are obtained in each classified problem within the individual layer. The continuity conditions at layer interfaces and the boundary conditions are then applied to solve the entire problem. Numerical results obtained using the current research show general agreement with existing solutions for end deflection and more complicated stress and displacement distributions which differ significantly from existing solutions.

GOVERNING EQUATIONS

The C-block actuators are constructed out of two curved piezoelectric layers in a bimorph configuration resulting in a half circle as shown in Fig. 1. The piezoelectric layers are surrounded on both sides by an electrode layer of silver ink. The bonding layer consists of a common epoxy used to connect the two piezoelectric layers. These layers are actuated with equal but opposite electric fields to produce a bending moment which is used as the actuation mechanism. The ratio of total actuator thickness to the piezoelectric material thickness is

small^[6]. The general governing equations for the C-block actuator, which is valid within each layer, is developed here based on the linear theory of elasticity. For a two dimensional elastic body defined in a cylindrical coordinate system (r, θ) (see Fig.1), the compatibility equations are written in terms of the normal strains ε_r and ε_θ , defined along the radial and the circumferential direction, respectively, and the shear strain $\gamma_{r\theta}$ as follows^[7].

$$\left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta^2} - r \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \right) \varepsilon_r + r \frac{\partial^2}{\partial r^2} (r \varepsilon_\theta) - \frac{\partial^2}{\partial r \partial \theta} (r \gamma_{r\theta}) = 0 \quad (1)$$

For actuators with induced strain, constitutive relations are written within an individual layer, as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_r &= a_{11}\sigma_r + a_{12}\sigma_\theta + a_{16}\tau_{r\theta} \\ \varepsilon_\theta &= a_{12}\sigma_r + a_{22}\sigma_\theta + a_{26}\tau_{r\theta} + \Lambda \\ \gamma_{r\theta} &= a_{16}\sigma_r + a_{26}\sigma_\theta + a_{66}\tau_{r\theta} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where, a_{ij} are the compliances for anisotropic material and Λ is the induced strain due to actuation. Denoting d_{31} as the piezoelectric coefficient and E_3 as the applied electric field, the induced strain can be expressed as

$$\Lambda = d_{31}E_3 \quad (3)$$

In each individual layer, the stress function is employed to solve the problem. The stress components can be expressed in terms of the stress function, ϕ , as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_r &= \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial \theta^2} - \frac{a_{16}a_{26} - a_{12}a_{66}}{\Delta} \Lambda \\ \sigma_\theta &= \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial r^2} - \frac{a_{11}a_{66} - a_{12}^2}{\Delta} \Lambda \\ \tau_{r\theta} &= -\frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial r \partial \theta} \left(\frac{\phi}{r} \right) - \frac{a_{12}a_{16} - a_{11}a_{26}}{\Delta} \Lambda \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where

$$\Delta = a_{11}a_{22}a_{66} + 2a_{12}a_{16}a_{26} - a_{22}a_{16}^2 - a_{11}a_{26}^2 - a_{12}a_{66}^2 \quad (5)$$

Using Eqs.(1), (2) and (4), the compatibility equation for anisotropic composite material can finally be written in terms of the stress function.

$$\begin{aligned} &\left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta^2} - r \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \right) \left[a_{11} \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial r} + \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial \theta^2} \right) + a_{12} \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial r^2} - a_{16} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial r \partial \theta} \left(\frac{\phi}{r} \right) \right] + r^2 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial r^2} \left[a_{12} \left(\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial \theta^2} \right) + \right. \\ &\left. a_{22} r \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial r^2} - a_{26} r \frac{\partial^2}{\partial r \partial \theta} \left(\frac{\phi}{r} \right) \right] - \frac{\partial^2}{\partial r \partial \theta} \left[a_{16} \left(\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial \theta^2} \right) + a_{26} r \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial r^2} - a_{66} r \frac{\partial^2}{\partial r \partial \theta} \left(\frac{\phi}{r} \right) \right] = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Since the induced strain is constant within the piezoelectric layer, it automatically disappears in Eq.(6) after taking derivatives.

ELASTICITY SOLUTION

According to the linear theory of piezoelectricity, the supposition technique can be used to simplify the solution procedure. Therefore, the general problem associated with the C-block actuators is classified into a few basic problems, such as the C-block with only induced strain, the C-block with an end moment and the C-block with an end force (Fig.2). In each one of these problems, the solution forms are defined in accordance to its characteristics. This is the key issue in this research.

Induced Strain

For C-blocks with only induced strain, the behavior characters are identical along the circumferential direction (except at the very near field at tow ends). Therefore, it is an axisymmetric problem. The solution can be obtained with the help of a stress function depending only on the single variable, r , that is, $\phi = \phi(r)$. Assuming

$$F = \frac{\partial \phi(r)}{\partial r} \tag{7}$$

Eqs.(4) and (6) yield the following

$$(a_{22}rF' + a_{12}F)' - (a_{12}F' + a_{11}F/r) = (a_{22} - a_{11})C_o \tag{8}$$

Fig.2 Modeling technique

where ()' is refers to differentiation. Let $r = e^t$ and $\dot{F} = \frac{dF}{dt}$, then the characteristic equation of Eq.(7) can be expressed as follows.

$$a_{22}\ddot{F} - a_{11}F = 0 \tag{9}$$

Solving Eq.(9), the two roots are obtained

$$\lambda_{1,2} = \pm \sqrt{\frac{a_{11}}{a_{22}}} \quad (10)$$

Therefore, the solution of the specified stress function F takes the following form

$$F = A_0 r^{\lambda_1} + B_0 r^{\lambda_2} + C_0 r \quad (11)$$

The material axes and the geometric coordinates in the C-blocks are identical, which yields $a_{16} = a_{26} = 0$. Using Eqs.(4) and (11), the following expressions are obtained for the stresses

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_r &= \frac{F}{r} + \frac{a_{12}}{a_{11}a_{22}} \Lambda = A_0 r^{\lambda_1-1} + B_0 r^{\lambda_2-1} + C_0 + \frac{a_{12}}{a_{11}a_{22}} \Lambda \\ \sigma_\theta &= F' - \frac{a_{11}a_{66} - a_{12}^2}{a_{11}a_{22}a_{66}} \Lambda = A_0 \lambda_1 r^{\lambda_1-1} + B_0 \lambda_2 r^{\lambda_2-1} + C_0 - \frac{a_{11}a_{66} - a_{12}^2}{a_{11}a_{22}a_{66}} \Lambda \\ \tau_{r\theta} &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where, A_0 , B_0 and C_0 are unknown constants which will be solved only after the global equations is established. Using the stress expressions in Eq.(12), the strain components can be obtained by using Eq.(2). The displacements at the radial direction u and the circumferential direction v can also be derived using following equations.

$$\varepsilon_r = \frac{\partial u}{\partial r}, \quad \varepsilon_\theta = \frac{u}{r} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial v}{\partial \theta}, \quad \gamma_{r\theta} = \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial u}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial r} - \frac{v}{r} \quad (13)$$

As noted before, the stress and displacement solutions, Eqs.(12) and (13), are only valid within each individual layer. To derive the global equation for the entire C-block, the continuity equation at layer interfaces and the boundary conditions at two ends, top and bottom surfaces are must be applied. Using the superscription (i) to identify quantities in the i^{th} layer and h_i to denote the thickness of the i^{th} layer ($i=1,2,\dots,k$, where k is the number of layers), the tractions and displacements at the layer interfaces must satisfy the following continuity equations defined in the local coordinate

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_{r\theta}^{(i)}(h_i, \theta) &= \tau_{r\theta}^{(i+1)}(h_i, \theta), & \sigma_r^{(i)}(h_i, \theta) &= \sigma_r^{(i+1)}(h_i, \theta) \\ u^{(i)}(h_i, \theta) &= u^{(i+1)}(h_i, \theta), & v^{(i)}(h_i, \theta) &= v^{(i+1)}(h_i, \theta) \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

The boundary conditions at the top and the bottom surfaces of the C-block are as follows.

$$\tau_{yz}(r_i, \theta) = \tau_{yz}(r_e, \theta) = 0, \quad \sigma_r(r_i, \theta) = \sigma_r(r_e, \theta) = 0 \quad (15)$$

where, r_i and r_e are the radius of the inner surface and the outer surface of the C-block, respectively. The boundary conditions at the clamped end, $\theta = 0$, are

$$u = v = \frac{\partial v}{\partial r} = 0, \quad \text{at } r = \frac{r_i + r_e}{2} \quad (16)$$

The boundary conditions at the free end, $\theta = \pi$, in this case are

$$\int_{r_i}^{r_e} \sigma_{\theta} dr = \int_{r_i}^{r_e} \sigma_{\theta} r dr = 0 \quad (17)$$

Using Eqs.(12) - (16), the final global equation is constituted for the entire C-block to solve for the constants defined in Eq.(12) and in displacement formulas (not shown due to the length limit). In general, this equation can be expressed in matrix form as follows.

$$\mathbf{Ax} = \mathbf{f} \quad (18)$$

where, the vector \mathbf{x} consists of the undetermined constants in stress and displacement functions and the vector \mathbf{f} consists of applied displacements, the applied forces and the equivalent forces caused by induced strains.

End Moment

For C-blocks with only an end moment, M , a similar solution procedure described above are used. However, the induced strain Λ is set to zero in all equations, Eqs.(12) - (17), and the second equation in Eq.(12) is modified to take into account the free end moment as follows.

$$\int_{r_i}^{r_e} \sigma_{\theta} r dr = -M \quad (19)$$

End Force

For C-blocks with only an end force, P , the bending moment at any cross section is proportional the $\sin(\pi-\theta)$ and the normal stress σ_{θ} is proportional to the bending moment^[8]. The stress function is found to be in the form

$$\phi = F(r) \sin \alpha \quad (20)$$

where

$$\alpha = \pi - \theta \quad (21)$$

For C-block actuators, the material axes and the geometric coordinates are always identical. This implies that $a_{16} = a_{26} = 0$. Therefore, Eq.(6) is simplified as follows.

$$\left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta^2} - r \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \right) \left[a_{11} \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial r} + \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial \theta^2} \right) + a_{12} \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial r^2} \right] + r^2 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial r^2} \left[a_{12} \left(\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial \theta^2} \right) + a_{22} r \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial r^2} \right] + a_{66} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial r \partial \theta} \left[r \frac{\partial^2}{\partial r \partial \theta} \left(\frac{\phi}{r} \right) \right] = 0 \quad (22)$$

Substituting Eq.(20) into Eq.(22), the stress function, F , satisfy the following equation

$$r^4 F^{IV} + 2r^3 F''' - \beta r^2 F'' + \beta(rF' - F) = 0 \quad (23)$$

where

$$\beta = \frac{2a_{12} + a_{11} + a_{66}}{a_{22}} \quad (24)$$

Following the same solution procedure to the characteristic equation, described in Eqs.(9) - (11), the solution formulation in this case can be derived as

$$F = A_1 r^{\lambda_1} + B_1 r^{\lambda_2} + C_1 r + D_1 r \log r \quad (25)$$

with

$$\lambda_{1,2} = 1 \pm \sqrt{1 + \beta} \quad (26)$$

Therefore, the stress components can be written as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_r &= \left(\frac{F'}{r} - \frac{F}{r^2} \right) \sin \alpha = \left[A_1 (\lambda_1 - 1) r^{\lambda_1 - 2} + B_1 (\lambda_2 - 1) r^{\lambda_2 - 2} + D_1 r^{-1} \right] \sin \alpha \\ \sigma_\theta &= F'' \sin \alpha = \left[A_1 \lambda_1 (\lambda_1 - 1) r^{\lambda_1 - 2} + B_1 \lambda_2 (\lambda_2 - 1) r^{\lambda_2 - 2} + D_1 r^{-1} \right] \sin \alpha \\ \tau_{r\theta} &= - \left(\frac{F}{r} \right)' \cos \alpha = - \left[A_1 (\lambda_1 - 1) r^{\lambda_1 - 2} + B_1 (\lambda_2 - 1) r^{\lambda_2 - 2} + D_1 r^{-1} \right] \cos \alpha \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

Next, the procedure described in Eqs.(13) - (17) is followed to derive the global equation governing the entire C-block actuator. An additional boundary condition describing the free end force is required to solve for all the unknown constants, and is

$$\int_{r_i}^{r_e} \tau_{r\theta} dr = -P \quad (28)$$

The final step involves the superposition of all three solutions to characterize the general behavior of the C-block actuators.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Numerical results obtained using the current elasticity approach are compared with those obtained using the existing curved beam approach^[2-4], the first-order shear deformation theory based approach^[5] and the classical elasticity solution with only the equivalent moment^[6]. The material properties used for the C-blocks are listed in Table 1, where the subscripts *p*, *b*, *e* are used to denote the properties for the piezoelectric layer, the bonding layer and the electrode layer, respectively, *E* is the Young's modulus and *ν* is the Poisson's ratio. The dimensions of the C-blocks are listed in Table 2, where *t* represents of the layer thickness. In all example, the induced strains have the same magnitude and the opposite sign in different layers.

Table 1. Material properties and miscellaneous parameters.

Material Properties		Other Parameters	
E_b (N/m ²)	1.9x10 ⁹	v_{max} (volts)	500
E_p (N/m ²)	5.4x10 ⁹	E_3 (V/m)	30.0x10 ⁵
E_e (N/m ²)	7.0x10 ⁸	d_{31} (m/V)	2.3x10 ⁻¹¹
ν_p	0.31	ν_b, ν_e	0.25

Table 2. Dimensions of the C-Blocks

Property	Two Layer Thick	Two Layer Thin	Three Layer
t_b (mm)	0.0	0.0	0.020
t_e (mm)	0.0	0.0	0.0
t_p (mm)	0.035	0.0007	0.025
r_i (mm)	0.065	14.9883	0.065
r_e (mm)	0.135	15.0117	0.135

In Fig.3, comparisons are made to examine the end deflection of both thin and thick two layered C-blocks with only the induced strain. The solution excluding the local induced strain effect can be calculated from classical elasticity method for curved beams with an equivalent moment. The current elasticity solution agrees with the existing curved beam approach, while both the first-order theory based approach and the classical elasticity solution over estimate the end deflection. This indicates that transverse effects tend to make the end deflection larger and the local induced strain effect reduces the end deflection. Finally these two effects cancel out with each other in the presence of only induced strain. This explains why the curved beam approach^[2,3], although technically inaccurate since it excludes both of these effects, arrives at the right numbers and also shows good correlations with the experimental data^[2-4].

The stress distributions of a thick two-layered C-block actuator are presented in Figs.4 and 5. The local induced strain dramatically changes the stress distributions. The current elasticity solution shows reduction in both maximum normal stress in circumferential direction and maximum transverse normal stress in radial direction due to the local induced strain effect. The maximum stress in circumferential direction is reduced by more than 50 percent and the maximum transverse normal stress in radial direction is reduced by approximately 34 percent compared to the classical elasticity solution. The induced strain effect also causes the discontinuity of the stress distribution or its slope at the layer interface. This phenomenon, generally observed at the layer interface of composite laminates with different ply orientations, is observed here for C-blocks with identical piezoelectric layers.

Fig.3 Comparison of end deflection for both thin and thick two layered C-blocks

Fig.4 Comparison of transverse normal stress through two layered C-block thickness

Fig.5 Comparison of normal stress through two layered C-block thickness

Fig.6 Comparison of circumferential displacement at free end for two layered C-block

Fig.7 Comparison of radial displacement at free end for two layered C-block

The displacement distributions of the thick two layered C-block actuator are also shown in Figs.6 and 7. The local induced strain also changes the displacement distributions resulting in reduced displacements in the current elasticity solution. The local induced strain effect reduces the circumferential displacement by about 11% and the radial displacement by about 12% compared to the classical elasticity solution. The induced strain effect also causes the slope discontinuity of the radial displacement at the layer interface and changes its shape. This is also a phenomenon that is generally observed for composites with different layers.

In the next example, an end resistant force (Fig.2) is considered in conjunction with piezoelectric actuations for a three layered C-block actuator. In this example, the end resistant force is set to be 1 N/m and its direction of application is assumed to be opposite to the end deflection due to the induced strain. Figures 8-10 present the stress distributions for C-blocks without and with the end resistant force. The end resistant force dramatically changes the stress distributions, particularly for the transverse normal and the transverse shear stresses. It reduces the normal stress in circumferential direction and increases the transverse normal stress. The magnitudes of these changes depend on the magnitude of the end resistant force. Again, the transverse normal stress and the transverse shear stress change their slopes at layer interface and the circumferential normal stress shows discontinuity at the layer interface. It is noted that with presence of the end resistant force, the transverse shear deformation becomes significant. As shown in Figs.8 and 9, the transverse shear stress is larger than the transverse normal stress. Since shear modulus of a material is much smaller compared to its Young's modulus, the evidence indicates that the transverse shear deformation can be significantly larger. As mentioned before, the transverse normal effect is an important factor for C-blocks with only the induced strain. In the presence of the end resistant force, the transverse shear effect is expected to play more important role in the mechanical behavior of C-block actuators.

Fig.8 Transverse normal stress distribution near the clamped end for three layered C-block

Fig.9 Transverse shear stress distribution at $\theta = 90^\circ$ for three layered C-block

Fig.10 Normal stress distribution near the clamped end for three layered C-block

CONCLUSIONS

An elasticity solution is developed for the mechanical behavior of polymeric piezoelectric c-block composite actuators, which were developed recently to overcome the limitations of conventional bimorph and stack piezoelectric configurations. Since the solutions are exact within the assumptions of linear piezoelectricity, they are free from the simplifying assumptions imposed by the existing approaches. Therefore no distinctions need to be made in the analysis for thick or thin C-blocks and both transverse shear deformation and transverse normal deformation are automatically taken into account. The following important observations have been made from this study.

- (1) The developed solution technique provides a framework against which comparisons can be made of classical and other existing approaches. It also provides insight into the basis of assumptions that are necessary in the formulation of a more general theory for curved actuators.
- (2) The current elasticity solution for end deflections agree well with the existing curved beam approach which have been validated through experiments.
- (3) The transverse deformation and the local induced strain have the opposite effects on end deflections. Refined approaches including only one of these effects will introduce more error than the simple approach which excludes both.
- (4) The local effect of the induced strain dramatically changes the stress and displacement distributions and causes the discontinuity of these distributions or their slopes at the layer interface for multilayered C-blocks.
- (5) The transverse shear deformation is more critical in the case of multilayered C-blocks with the end resistant force.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The research is supported by the Air Force Office of Scientific Research, grant number: F49620-96-0195, technical monitor Dr. Brian Sanders.

REFERENCES

1. Crawley, E. F. and de Luis, J., "Use of Piezoelectric Actuators as Elements of Intelligent Structures", *AIAA Journal*, Vol. 5, No. 10, 1987, pp. 1373-1385.
2. Brei, D., "Design and Development of a New Class of Piezoelectric Actuators for Force Improvement", *Proc Society of Engineering Science 31st Annual Technical Meeting*, College Station TX, Oct. 10-12, 1994.
3. Brei, D., "Design and Development of a Piezoelectric Microactuator Building Block for Deflection Improvement" *Proc. Symposium on Micro-Mechanical Systems*, ASME Winter Annual Meeting, Chicago IL, Vol. 2., Nov. 6-11, 1994, pp. 717-723.
4. Seeley, C. E., Chattopadhyay, A. and Brei, D., "Development of a Piezoelectric C-block Actuator Using Hybrid Optimization Technique", *AIAA Journal*, Vol. 34, No.1, 1996, pp. 123-128.
5. Chattopadhyay, A., Mitchell, L.A. and Gu, H., Refined Modeling of Adaptive Composites with Curved Actuators, *Society of Engineering Science, 33rd Annual Technical Meeting Smart Structures and Materials Symposium*, Oct.20-23, 1996, Tempe, AZ
6. Crawley, E. F. and Anderson, E. H., "Detailed Models of Piezoelectric Actuation of Beams", *Proc. of the 30th AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS/ASC Structures, Structural Dynamics and Materials Conference*, Mobile, Al., April 1989, pp. 2000-2010.
7. Lekhnitskii, S. G., *Theory of Elasticity of an Anisotropic Body*, Mir Publishers, Moscow, 1981
8. Timoshenko, S. P. and Goodier, J. N., *Theory of Elasticity*, International student Edition, McGraw-Hill Kogakusha, Ltd., 1970